

**PREVALENCE OF EXTRAGENITAL DISEASES IN PREGNANT
WOMEN OF BUKHARA REGION**

Hamidova Nozima Komilovna

Bukhara State Medical Institute

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Extragenital pathology includes a large group of diverse and ambiguous diseases, clinical syndromes and conditions, and these diseases are united by the fact that they are not obstetric complications of pregnancy and gynecological diseases. Pregnancy has a negative effect on the course of extragenital pathology. The most well-known adverse effect of normal gestational changes in hemodynamics on the course of most heart diseases [1].

The adverse effect of extragenital pathology on the course of pregnancy, childbirth and the postpartum period is diverse and depends on the nature and severity of the underlying disease. Many extragenital diseases (EGZ) predispose to the development of obstetric complications. It can be said that EGZ increases the risk of premature placental abruption and eclampsia, all hemophilic conditions – early postpartum bleeding, diabetes mellitus – labor abnormalities, fetal distress, shoulder dystocia, urinary tract infection – premature birth, etc. [2].

Currently, with most EGZ, it is possible to safely carry out pregnancy and childbirth, provided that the woman is properly monitored during pregnancy, and, if necessary, special treatment is prescribed [3].

The purpose of the study: to study the frequency and structure of extragenital pathology in pregnant women of the Bukhara region.

Materials and methods: To study the frequency and structure of extragenital pathology, the birth histories of pregnant women hospitalized in the Bukhara Regional Perinatal Center in the periods from 2017 to 2019 were retrospectively studied. Statistical analysis of the obtained results was carried out using methods of variational statistics.

Results and their discussion: The results of a retrospective analysis for the last 3 years (2017-2019) showed that 19,403 births were registered in the Bukhara region. Among them, physiological childbirth was registered in 7393 (38.1%), and pathological childbirth in 11911 (61.4%) pregnant women. When studying the etiological factors of pathological childbirth in the Bukhara region, various EHS were established in pregnant women, which averaged 1,660 cases (4.35%) over the studied period. The structure of the EGZ of pregnant women was dominated by acute respiratory viral infections, severe anemia (≤ 70 g/l) and

obesity, which accounted for 29.7%, 21.6% and 17.9% of cases. Over the past 2 years (2018-2019), thyroid pathology prevailed among all EGZ in pregnant women, which in 2018 amounted to 21.9% and in 2019 - 14.4%, respectively, which in most cases confirms the presence of iodine deficiency and the course of pregnancy against the background of thyroid pathology.

Conclusions: Thus, the study of the structure of EGZ in pregnant women reveals some aspects of the course of pregnancy and the outcomes of childbirth associated with the endocrine-biochemical status of the maternal organism. All this proves the need to optimize the management of pregnancy and childbirth in women with EGZ, as well as the development of algorithms for the management of childbirth of pregnant women in this category. Timely pre-pregnancy preparation and correction of complications ensures a favorable course of pregnancy and childbirth, as well as a reduction in the frequency of miscarriage.

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